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Road Map of Seasonal Wild Edible Plants from the Forest to local markets

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Abstract

Utilization of wild edible plants is significant for supplementing food resources and uplifting the economy of the local people. Indigenous peoples of Manipur, Northeast India are collecting and using wild edible plants for different purposes. In the state of Manipur, there is traditional supply chain of wild edible plants. The present paper aims to highlight the common seasonally marketed wild edible plants in Manipur and to map the existing value chains of wild edible plants to enhance the economy of the peoples of our state Manipur. The paper also analyzed the present scenario of the market trends of wild edible plants including market demand and supply chain dynamics. About 80 species were collected from the market survey and categorized 20 species each of the three consecutive months, November- January, February-April, May-July, August-October. Some of the species are collected repeatedly from one category to another because they can grow throughout the year also.

Keywords: Wild Edible plants; Market; Supply chain; Value chain

1. Introduction

From time immemorial, human beings are dependent on various plant resources to fulfill their daily needs. All over the world, people are collecting many wild edible plants including non-timber forest products for various purposes. Interest in the growing potential of non-timber forest products has been inspired by desire to promote traditional values, use of natural products and acceptance of the importance of sustainability [1]. The potential of studies on non-timber forest products have gone beyond the narrow rural focus of previous studies [2]. Non-timber forest products have many values in different uses. They can be used as edible products or medicinal and dietary supplements. Out of these different products, wild edible plants play a very important role in the traditional community by providing food resources as well as sustenance to the local economy.

According to the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO), wild edible plants are those plants which can grow spontaneously in natural or semi-natural ecosystems and can live independently from human action [3]. WEPs are neither cultivated nor domesticated but locally available as food resources based on traditional knowledge. The mode of use of the WEPs depends on the availability area, their seasonality and specificity in culture and tradition. WEPs play an important role in reducing poverty, improving food security, diversifying agriculture, generating income and preventing malnutrition [4]. Some researchers also highlight the nutritional benefits of WEPs showing presence of minerals, vitamins, carbohydrates, proteins, fats and fiber.

The state Manipur has diverse ethnic groups and has a long history of utilizing plants according to their traditional practices, consuming various plant parts based on knowledge passed down through generation to generation. These diverse communities have traditional knowledge for using rich forest resources and associated knowledge provide captivating backdrop of ethnobotanical studies. Various ethnobotanical works have been published across the state

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focusing on ethnobotany particularly the traditional knowledge and practices of these different ethnic communities. The first botanical exploration of Manipur was made by G. Watt. who served as a botanist during the boundary survey of (1881-1882) [5]. In the state of Manipur, prominent ethnobotanical work was believed to be pioneered by [6]. After this, numerous ethnobotanists have been working by the growing interest of the wild food plants in the contemporary communities [7,8,9,10, 11, 12].

Identification and proper intervention in their harvesting and supply chains could contribute to the supplementation of food resources, nutritional security as well as the economy of the stakeholders [12]. Wild edible plants play a very important role for household food security and community at higher levels; thus, it is essential that socio-ecological system for gathering and marketing these natural resources be appropriately managed, protected and prevented from overexploitation and deforestation. [13, 14].

It has been estimated that at least one billion people are using wild foods to supplement diets [15]. Increasing the rate of deforestation during the last few years has affected the availability of wild edible plants. Increasing population and lack of communication also contribute to the increased harvesting of wild plants. In many cases, harvesting wild edible plants are not regulated or poorly restricted by those people depending on these plants for their economic sustenance.

A value chain has series of steps or value-creating activities that connect the natural sources of the wild plants to the consumers from markets. This connecting series cannot be isolated from one another. In the content of wild edible plants value chain describes the sequence of activities required to make a finished product from its initial starting material such as field crops or gathered wild material [16]. Analysis of value chain is a useful method for understanding how markets operate for a particular good [17]. It helps in understanding the value-added services through which the item comes from the initial production stage to final delivering consumers. Analysis of value chain encompasses all the activities and services required to bring a particular product or services from its conception to destination either local, national, regional or global markets.[18].

The identification of the key actors and their role in the system can be done by development of value chain map. [19]. Understanding value chain actors and enhancing or modifying their role is important for increasing economic contribution of forest resources [20]. Manipur, one of the Northeastern State of India has a diverse community with rich tradition of collecting and marketing wild edible plants for their economic sustenance. The state having different communities such as *Meitei*, *Meitei Pangal*, Naga, Kuki, each of them having their own traditional system of collecting, preserving and consumption of the wild edible plants.

Figure 1 Map of India showing the Location of State Manipur

Figure 2 Markets of Bishnupur dist.

Figure 3 Khwairamband bazar in Imphal west district

In the past, there was closely related and giving corporation between the peoples of hills and involving forming a unique system of corporative marketing. Among different communities of Manipur making trade-partners. Not only this, but channel partners are also formed between members of different communities residing in different geographical areas i.e. hills and plains.

In Manipur making of trade-partners commonly known as "*Ngai sanaba*" occur between the families of hills and valleys. Agricultural and forest products that are harvested by one partner would be sold only with their corresponding partner in another village. A strong economic bond was made to maintain the harmony and cultural relationship between different communities. However, the value chain system something different from the past years due to the present conflict between *Meitei* and *Kuki* communities. The *Meitei* traders could not enter freely to the hilly areas because of the present situation. Thus, the intermediate community i.e. *Meitei Pangal* take important role for taking the forest products which are harvested by the hilly peoples and lastly those items reach to the plain areas. Presently, the villagers of different communities collect the WEPs from the nearby forest and sell them to village market. Harvest and trade of wild edible plants are closely linked and dependent on each other for sustaining agricultural products. The traders collect the items from the village market or the harvested areas and bring them to the heart of the city and deliver them to the consumers. The objectives of the study are: (i) To identify the common seasonally marketed wild edible plants in Manipur and (ii) To analyze the map of existing value chains of wild edible plants to enhance the livelihood of the local peoples.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Area

The present work was conducted in Northeastern state of Manipur. The boundaries of the state are – Myanmar border the state on the east and bounded on the north by Nagaland, Assam on the West and South by Mizoram states of India. Primary data was collected from different markets of different districts. Market surveys were done at the village markets, i.e. Moirang Bazar Ningthoukhong Bazar, Bishnupur Bazar, Nambol Bazar and Imphal Bazar (Khwairamband Market) where WEPs traded. Table 1 shows the name of the study markets with districts. Information about the origin of the item and price of that item were collected from the sellers, collectors, middlemen and consumers.

Table 1 Location of markets where primary data was collected

Sl. No.	Name of the village with districts	Name of the markets
1	Moirang (Bishnupur district)	Moirang Bazar
2	Ningthoukhong (Bishnupur district)	Bishnupur Bazar
3	Nambol (Bishnupur district)	Nambol Bazar
4	Imphal (Imphal West district)	Khwairamband Bazar

2.2. Interviews

Questionnaires were conducted to the collectors to get information about the wild edible plants which were found in the markets. While collecting the information, consider only those plants which were considered as wild edible plants. Market surveys were done by visiting the markets from January 2022 to July 2025. Data was collected for availability, seasonality and supply-chains of different wild edible plants. To supplement the market data several WEPs traders were also interviewed to understand the source, availability, demand and value of the plants. Moreover, several vendors, buyers or community members of that specific place were also interviewed to gather more information about the origin or availability and the trading system of the items.

3. Results and Discussion

The information was gathered from scientific research articles and published book chapters. Both online and offline journals were scrutinized. Data was mainly collected through interviews with the local people or stakeholders of those study areas. Value chain analysis was started by understanding the scope of supply chain structure [21, 22]. A supply chain structure was developed by identifying the stakeholder. By analyzing the supply chain, it could be helpful to identify the various marketed wild edible plants. From data analysis, the economic condition of the state can also be understood. In this analysis, the chain of activities that originate from conception to end used customers were strategically relevant to each other.

Table 2 List of wild edible plants commonly marketed in the month of November-January

Scientific name	Vernacular name	Family	Types of food	Processing types	Availability [P=plenty, C=common, A=Abundant, R=Rare, L=Limited, Mo=Moderate, M=Moirang, Ni=Ningthoukhong, B=Bishnupur, Na=Nambol, Kh=Khwairamband]				
					M	Ni	B	Na	Kh
<i>Nymphaea pubescens</i> Willd.	Tharo	Nymphaeaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	P	C	C	A	R
<i>Cycas pectinata</i> Buch.Ham.	Yendang	Cycadaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	R	A	A	R	R
<i>Plantago major</i> L.	Yempat	Plantaginaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	R	R	R	A	L
<i>Marsilea quadrifolia</i> L.	Ising-yensang	Marsileaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	Mo	A	A	R	L
<i>Wendlandia tinctoria</i> Bartl.ex DC.	Pheija	Rubiaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	C	C	P	C	P
<i>Oenanthe javanica</i> (Blume)DC.	Comprek	Apiaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	P	C	C	C	P

<i>Anisomeles indica</i> (L.) Kuntze	<i>Thoiding amuba</i>	Lamiaceae	Seed	Sun dry	C	A	Mo	A	P
<i>Neptunia Oleracea</i> Lour	<i>Ekaithabi</i>	Fabaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	P	P	C	C	P
<i>Stelaria media</i> (L.) Vill	<i>Yerum kairum</i>	Caryophyllaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	A	A	R	R	P
<i>Persicaria posumbu</i> (Buch. -Ham.ex D.Don)	<i>Phakpai</i>	Polygonaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	C	R	R	A	R
<i>Alocasia cuculata</i> (Lour.) G.Don	<i>Honghu kakla</i>	Araceae	Vegetable	Fresh	C	C	C	C	C
<i>Hedychium coronarium</i> J.Koenig	<i>Takhelei angouba</i>	Zingiberaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	C	C	A	C	C
<i>Garcinia pedunculata</i> Roxb.ex Buch. - Ham	<i>Heibung</i>	Clusiaceae	Spices	Fresh, Sun dry	A	C	A	C	P
<i>Rhus chinensis</i> Mill.	<i>Heimang</i>	Anacardiaceae	Fruits	Fresh, sun dry	C	C	A	R	L
<i>Elaegnus conferta</i> Roxb	<i>Heiyai</i>	Elaeagnaceae	Fruit	Fresh	C	C	C	C	P
<i>Chenopodium album</i> L.	<i>Monsaobi</i>	Amaranthaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	R	R	R	A	C
<i>Pseudognaphalium luteoalbum</i> (L.) Hilliard & B.L.Burt.	<i>Phunil</i>	Asteraceae	Vegetable	Fresh	R	C	C	R	C
<i>Parkia speciosa</i> Hassk.	<i>Yongchak</i>	Fabaceae	Vegetable	Fresh, sun dry	C	C	C	C	P

Table 3 List of marketed wild edible plants in the month of February, March-April

Scientific name	Vernacular name	Family	Types of food	Processing type	Availability [P=plenty, C=common, A=Abundant, R=Rare, L=Limited, Mo=Moderate, M=Moirang, Ni=Ningthoukhong, B=Bishnupur, Na=Nambol, Kh=Khwairamband]				
					M	Ni	B	Na	Kh
<i>Hedychium flavum</i> , (J. Koenig)	Loklei	Zingiberaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	C	C	C	C	C
<i>Prunus domestica</i> (L.)	Heikha	Rosaceae	Fruits	Fresh	C	C	C	C	C
<i>Prunus cerasoides</i> , D. Don	Malhei	Rosaceae	Fruits	Fresh	C	C	C	C	C

<i>Tetrastigma leucostaphylum</i> , (Dennst.)	Monjamhei	Vitaceae	Fruits	Fresh	R	R	L	L	C
<i>Baccaurea sapida</i> , (Roxb.)	Motokhei	Phyllanthaceae	Fruits	fresh	R	R	L	L	C
<i>Curcuma angustifolia</i> , (Roxb.)	Yaipal	Zingiberaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	C	C	A	C	P
<i>Alpinia nigra</i> , (Gaertn.)	Pullei	Zingiberaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	A	C	C	C	P
<i>Lentinus squarrosulus</i> , (L.)	U-Yen	Polypora ceae	Vegetable	Fresh, sun dry	R	C	C	C	A
<i>Oenanthe javanica</i> , (Blume)DC	Comprek	Apiaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	P	C	C	C	P
<i>Allium hookerii</i> , Thwaites.	Maroinakupi	Amaryllidaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	C	C	C	C	P
<i>Parkia speciosa</i> , Hassk.	Yongchak	Fabaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	C	C	C	C	P
<i>Pseudognaphalium luteoalbum</i> , (L.)	Phunil	Asteracea	Vegetable	Fresh	R	R	R	R	P
<i>Persicaria posumbu</i> , Buch.	Phakpai	Polygonaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	R	R	R	R	C
<i>Chenopodium album</i> (L.)	Monsaobi	Amarantheceae	Vegetable	Fresh	R	R	R	R	L
<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> (L.)	Chengkruk	Amaranthaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	R	R	R	R	C

Table 4 Marketed wild edible plants found in the month of May – July

Scientific name	Vernacular name	Family	Types of food	Processing types	Availability [P=plenty, C=common, A=Abundant, R=Rare, L=Limited, Mo=Moderate, M=Moirang, Ni=Ningthoukhong, B=Bishnupur, Na=Nambol, Kh=Khwairamband				
					M	Ni	B	Na	Kh
<i>Allium hookerii</i> Twaittes	Maroi napakpi	Amaryllidaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	C	C	C	C	A
<i>Allium tuberosum</i> Rottler ex Spreng.	Maroi nakupi	Amaryllidaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	C	C	A	A	P
<i>Eryngium foetidum</i> , (L.)	Awa phadigom	Apiaceae	V	F	C	C	A	C	P
<i>Neptunia oleracea</i> , Lour.	Ising ekaithabi	Fabaceae	V	F	P	C	C	P	P

<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> , Gaertn.	Thamchet	Nelumbonaceae	S	F	P	C	C	A	P
<i>Euryale ferox</i> , Salisb.	Thangjing	Nymphaeaceae	S	F	P	C	C	C	P
<i>Colocasia esculanta</i> , Schott	Paan	Araceae	V	F	C	C	C	C	P
<i>Garcinia xanthochymus</i> , (Hook.f.)	Heibung	Clusiaceae	F	F	C	C	C	C	P
<i>Centella asiatica</i> , (L.)	Peruk	Apiaceae	V	F	C	C	C	C	C
<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> , (L.)	Pakhangleiton	Euphorbiaceae	V	F	R	R	R	R	R
<i>Melocanna bambusoides</i> Trin.	Moubi wa	Poaceae	C	C	P	C	C	C	C
<i>Crotalaria juncea</i> , (L.)	U-hawaimaton	Fabaceae	R	R	R	R	R	R	R
<i>Trapa natans</i> , (L.)	Heikak	Lythraceae	Plenty	C	C	C	C	C	C

Table 5 Wild edible plants which found in the month of August - October

Botanical name	Vernacular name	Family	Types of food	Processing type	Availability [P=plenty, A=Abundant, L=Limited, M=Moirang, Ni=Ningthoukhong, B=Bishnupur, Kh=Khwairamband, C=common, R=Rare, Mo=Moderate, Na=Nambol]				
					M	Ni	B	Na	Kh
<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i> Lam	Theibong	Moraceae	Fruit, seed	Fresh	C	C	A	R	R
<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> Gaertn.	Thamchet	Nelumbonaceae	Seed	Fresh	A	C	C	C	C
<i>Euryale ferox</i> Salisb.	Thangjing	Nymphaeaceae	Seed	Fresh	C	C	C	C	A
<i>Rush chinensis</i> , Mill	Heimang	Anacardiaceae	Seed	Fresh, sun dry	C	C	C	C	C
<i>Elsholtzia blanda</i> , Benth.	Lomba	Lamiaceae	Spice	Fresh, sun dry	C	C	C	C	C
<i>Ocimum americanum</i> , (L.)	Mayangton	Lamiaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	C	C	C	C	C
<i>Zizania latifolia</i> Griseb.	Esing-Kambong	Poaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	C	R	R	R	C

<i>Schizophyllum commune</i> Fr.	Kanglayan	Schizophyllaceae	Vegetable	Fresh.Sun dry	R	C	C	R	C
<i>Termitomyces eurrhizus</i> Berk.	Naril chengum	Lyophyllaceae	Vegetable	Fresh	R	C	C	R	C
<i>Auricularia delicata</i> , Bull.	Uchina	Auriculariaceae	Fungi	Fresh, Sun dry	C	C	C	C	C
<i>Volvariella volvacea</i> , Bull.	Charuyen	Auriculariaceae	Mushroom	Fresh	R	C	C	C	C
<i>Gacinia xanthochymus</i> , Hook.f.	Heirangoi	Clusiaceae	Fruit	Fresh	R	R	R	R	L
<i>Averrhoa carambola</i> , (L.)	Heinoujom	Oxalidaceae	Fruit	Fresh	C	C	C	C	C
<i>Phyllanthus acidus</i> , (L.)	Gihori	Phyllanthaceae	Fruit	fresh	C	C	C	C	C

Table 6 List of the marketed wild edible plants throughout the year with market value

Botanical name	Vernacular name	Family	Growth habit	Parts used	Types of processing	Price per unit
<i>Allium hookeri</i> , Thwaites.	Maroi napakpi	Amarillidaceae	Herb	Whole parts	Fresh	Rs.10 per bundle
<i>Allium tuberosum</i> , Rolter ex Spreng.	Maroi nakupi	Amaryllidaceae	Herb	Whole parts	Fresh	Rs.10 per bundle
<i>Eryngium faetidum</i> , (L.)	Awa phadigom	Apiaceae	Herb	Whole parts	Fresh	Rs.10 per bundle
<i>Centella asiatica</i> , (L.)	Peruk	Apiaceae	Herb	Whole parts	Fresh	Rs.20 per bunch
<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i> , Forssk.	Kolamni	Convolvulaceae	Herb	Whole parts	Fresh	Rs.10 bundle
<i>Oenanthe aquatica</i> , (L.)	Comprek	Apiaceae	Herb	Whole plant	Fresh	Rs.10 per bundle
<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> , (L.)	Chengkruk	Amaranthaceae	Herb	Young shoot	Fresh	Rs.20 per bunch
<i>Plantago major</i> , (L.)	Yempat	Plantaginaceae	Herb	Whole parts	Fresh	Rs.20 per bundle
<i>Juglans regia</i> , (L.)	Heijugak	Juglandaceae	Tree	Seed	Dry seeds	Rs.80/250g
<i>Schizophyllum commune</i> , Fr.	Kanglayan	Schizophyllaceae	Mushroom fungus	Whole parts	Dried mushroom	Rs. 100/250g
<i>Lentinus squarrosulus</i> , (Month.)	Uyen	Polyporaceae	Fungus	Whole parts	Dried food.	Rs. 100/250 g
<i>Auricularia delicata</i> , Bull.	Uchina	Auriculariaceae	Fungus	Whole parts	Fresh & Sun dry	Rs. 100/250g

<i>Zanthoxylum acanthopodium</i> , DC.	Mukthruhi	Rutaceae	Shrub	Leaves & young shoot	Fresh	Rs.10 per bundle
<i>Salvia dianthera</i> , Roth.	Kanghuman	Lamiaceae	Shrub	Leaves & young shoot	Fresh	Rs.10 per bundle
<i>Persicaria capilata</i> , Bush. - Ham	Phakpai	Polygonaceae	Herb	Leaves & Young shoot	Fresh	Rs. 10 per bundle
<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> , L.	Naoseklei	Lamiaceae	Herb	Leaves & young shoot	Fresh	Rs.10 per bundle
<i>Ocimum americanum</i> , (L.)	Mayangba	Lamiaceae	Herb	Leaves & Young shoot	Fresh	Rs.20 per bunch
<i>Houttuynia cordata</i> , Thunb.	Tuningkhok	Saururaceae	Herb	Whole parts	Fresh	Rs. 20 per bundle
<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i> , Bush. - Ham.	Tespata	Lauraceae	Tree	Leaves	Fresh, sun dry	Rs.20 per bunch

Figure 4 Habit wise distribution of marketed wild edible plants throughout the season related with the study markets

Figure 5 Family wise distribution of the marketed wild edible plants throughout the year

3.1. Value Chain of Wild Edible Plants

From the market survey and interaction with the stakeholders and villagers, value chain of some common wild edible plant is considered. Local people collect wild edible plants from the forest. In village, there is no community restriction for collecting wild edible plants. All the villagers have equitability in collection of forest resources. Sometimes, the neighboring villagers also come and collect the resources without restriction. Villagers collect wild edible plants without paying any royalty to the village authority. Most of the villagers do not pay the tax to the Forest Department, Government of Manipur, while collecting the plants from the Reserve Forest Area. The villagers collect the wild edible plants from the forest areas and sell them to the village markets with a few amounts. Then, the traders collect it and again sold to the large market areas which having large demanding of buyers with increasing amount. Thus, the amount of the specific item is different from one market to another.

3.2. Collection and processing wild edible plants from forest

There is gender discrimination in collection of WEPs from forest areas. Men can carry more items than the women. So, they are favorable in collection of the wild edible plants from the forest even though both men and women are involved in the collection of the plants. The collected plant volume is not depended to the market demand; it depends on how much a person can carry per trip as well as the availability of WEPs. This type of activity is a part of traditional lifestyle. The collection of the WEPs is also done by the government employees if they have spare time. The processing of wild edible plants is performed using different methods. Some of the methods are cut and clean at the collection site

Figure 6 Value chain of Agricultural products and Wild edible Plants

itself. This type of activity was performed to reduce the load of the materials. Fermentation is also done by preserving the products. Most of the wild edible plants may belong to either (a) used as raw, (b) dried or (c) processed e.g. fermentation etc. There are different methods for post processing treatment. Drying is one of the most common types of post processing treatment. Sun drying and drying over kitchen stove are some of the important drying techniques which were done by the villagers. Processing wild edible plants takes around 3-7 days.

3.3. Marketing Mode

In Manipur, mode of marketing is different from one village to another. In most cases, the collectors themselves bring the items to the village market and sell them directly to the consumers. In another case, the producers sell the items wholesale to local retailers. While selling to the retailers, the producers distributed all the items to different retailers because it is too risky to stock many products only in one retailer. Price fluctuation also occurs as well as profits at the retailers are also different. Table shows the change in selling units and prices between collectors and retailers for some selected wild edible plants in different markets are listed.

3.4. Actors in Chain

The actors take different roles in supply chain as well as value chain. Not only the villagers, but middlemen are also the actors of this supply chain. They belong to two categories – (i) Those peoples from outside the village (ii) from the village itself. In the present situation of the state Manipur, the role of the middlemen was taken by the *Meitei Pangal* (Muslim) communities. Due to the present conflict situation, Meiteis cannot enter freely to the hilly areas for collecting the wild edible plants. Thus, most of the wild edible plants from the hilly areas are collected and transported by the *Meitei Pangal* communities to the valley markets, after this the stakeholders collect it and again sold to the market and delivered by the consumers. Retailors again categorized into two – (i) Local Retailers who receive the items directly from the producers. (ii) Urban retailers who received the items from either wholesaler or middlemen. Retailers also cannot afford all the items carried by a collector due to the high amounts. Mostly, retailers go door to door to sell the items, or they settle at one place and sale the items. The size of the market is also different, one is big and another is small. The village markets are usually small and low amount of money can be invested by the stakeholders. The small markets have low demand, on the other hand the markets having high demand are big in size and the stakeholders also can sale the items by investing high amount of money. The rate of profit is also different from one place to another.

3.5. Relationship of WEPs with other Agri - products

WEPs have closely related to the other Agri-products because while selling the wild edible plants the seller, or the producers transported together and sold together with the other agri-products. The buyers also buy altogether, and consumers also consume the wild edible plants with the other Agri-products.

Successful commercialization of the products needs to identify wild edible plants and analysis the value chains of products. Wilds plants have potential in poverty reduction particularly in developing economy if the value chains are improved. [21]. Cultural services and values associated with WEPs are significant factors for the divergent consumption pattern for plant species [22]. Role of stakeholders are very significant and overlapped in three stages – at the producer's level, processing level and marketing level. In Manipur context, role of actors is not equal, producers take higher roles which role of middlemen is highly reduced. Increasing role of middlemen who serve the bridge between primary producer and retailer or end user may create complex value chains as observed in Asia countries particularly in wild medicinal plants [23]. The market of the wild edible plants is characterized by non-standardized measurement units, price fluctuation and minimum value addition. Whole villagers have equitable access to wild edible plant resources. Because of this, making chance of overharvesting is very high. Wild edible plants harvesting cannot continue indefinitely without proper management practices to sustain their yield [24]. Only those plants that can be harvested without killing the whole plants and have the capability to regenerate easily [24].

4. Conclusion

The trading system of WEPs in Manipur is mainly done through “supply driven chain” with significant role of collectors, producers and middlemen. There is a large potential of wild edible plants. The Northeast India has rich flora and fauna as well as most valuable wild edible plants are also available. These natural resources have great economic potential not only in the local level but also in the worldwide contexts. To study the channelizing of these resource potentials and value addition to these products in scientific process can contribute to the economic development of the local populations as well as increase food potentials. A long-term plan is needed for wild edible plants involving stakeholders and sustainability of the economic condition of the local villagers.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no any conflict of interest among the authors.

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